

Project Title **Implementing FAIR Workflows: a proof of concept study in the field of consciousness**

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D1.1 FAIR Workflows Specification

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Project summary

Formally published papers that have been through a peer review and editorial process remain the most important means of communicating science today. A major obstacle is that current research articles provide only a fraction of the information required to fully evaluate a scientific study. Articles provide a succinct description of the methods and work carried out as well as the conclusions drawn based on that work. Most of the time, there is no underlying information available and no mechanism to easily link the article to the experimental design, the research data, and the analytical tools that were used to generate the reported outcomes. This challenge prevents the research community from being able to fully understand the results of the research, to replicate its results, and to decisively evaluate, and reuse existing research. Availability of the different outputs of a research project would enable reuse of data and software in order to aggregate findings across studies to evaluate discoveries in the field, and ultimately to assess and accelerate progress.

As a consequence, there is currently a push to make science Open and FAIR¹ to increase reproducibility and reusability of scientific results, the most recent example being the White House OSTP memo², following the UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science³. Recognizing the importance of better management of research entities has led to critical advances concerning development of infrastructure for preregistration of studies, data repository platforms, standards for data sharing, and ontologies. As the research community increasingly embraces new forms of research outputs such as preregistration, protocols, datasets and software, new workflows and best practices need to be developed to establish openness, connectedness and to ensure interoperability across the full research cycle.

The FAIR workflows project seeks to contribute to these developments by providing an exemplar workflow which takes the concept of making one's research FAIR and open, and provides a concrete example and implementation based on the reality of an entire research investigation lifecycle. In collaboration with a team of neuroscience and consciousness researchers, the project tests the challenges of the research team, the time investments, the availability of the metadata and tools needed to ensure FAIR research outputs, and the ability of a dashboard to meaningfully contribute to the research workflow and the impact of research outputs. For FAIR workflows to become standard for all researchers, they will need to have easily implementable examples of how to make their research outputs FAIR and open, and this project will be impactful as a demonstration.

¹ <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>

² <https://www.osti.gov/2022-OSTP-Public-Access-Memo-Release>

³ <https://en.unesco.org/science-sustainable-future/open-science/recommendation>

Executive summary

Researchers are increasingly asked to make their research open and FAIR, but what does this mean in practice? In this project, the partners work together to create an exemplar implementation that will provide workflows that can be used by researchers within the field of consciousness and that can be adopted by other domains. This activity requires the development of a specification for the use of open scholarly infrastructure to support FAIR data and services for all entities running throughout the entire research lifecycle. The workflow is based on the use of existing persistent identifier systems and accompanying metadata.

Our approach to addressing these challenges is to ensure that the systems make outputs FAIR upon inception, at the time they get created by researchers. This process requires agreed-upon metadata standards that enable FAIRness.

In this document, we lay out the workflow we are following, and how this can be used by integrators and researchers. For integrators, we explain how the different project partners contribute to enhanced interoperability between systems to enable FAIR workflows. For researchers, we provide a step-by-step workflow explaining at which stage which outputs should be deposited, which PIDs can then be registered, and which metadata is needed to make the outputs—and the connections between outputs—available to the community.

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Introduction

The Implementing FAIR workflows project⁴ aims to build an exemplar workflow for researchers and research tools by working with a Cognitive Neuroscience research team to implement FAIR practices throughout a 3 year research project. Leveraging existing services and platforms that are integrated with open persistent identifier (PID) infrastructures, the project charts the way forward for researchers and research teams that are looking to take action towards making their research more reproducible and reusable, as well as potential integrators that are interested to provide support to research workflows and make concrete contributions to the scholarly infrastructure on a metadata level.

Research outputs are of inestimable value: they empower research, offer new perspectives and advance knowledge. Research results are increasingly relying on existing research data, protocols, methodologies and expertise. For this reason, the entirety of a research study should be shared with the research community and be Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR). In reality, research outputs are often stored decentrally, stored only temporarily, and not well described in the metadata. There is a lack of processes to support researchers and administrators in making all outputs FAIR, which would enable greater confidence in the research study as a whole.

As the Open Research community continues to embrace these emerging forms of research outputs such as preprints, datasets, software and pre-registered results, it is becoming more important to establish connectedness and to ensure interoperability. As a community, we are faced with the challenge that current research articles provide only a fraction of the information required to fully evaluate a scientific study. This project recognizes that a lot of important work has happened, and is ongoing, to implement the FAIR principles and maximize the use of research outputs. Therefore, this project aims to bring together a range of stakeholders with expertise in different areas and focus on interoperability and connectedness. This way, existing initiatives can be brought together to ensure no information is lost and provide a proof of concept that demonstrates implementation of FAIR workflows throughout the research lifecycle.

This document provides an overview of both aspects described above, by outlining the integrations planned in the project that support FAIR sharing of outputs, and the many outputs researchers can share during the various stages of the project lifecycle.

⁴ <https://doi.org/10.54224/20568>

What are FAIR Workflows

FAIR workflows are the workflows that pave the way for FAIR research outputs, the basis of reproducible and reusable research. For researchers, these are workflows to effectively share different types of outputs at each stage of research; for tools and platforms, these are workflows to evaluate and implement persistent identifier (PID) integrations to leverage open metadata infrastructure; for funders and research producing organizations, these are workflows to adopt PIDs into current practice and guide the researcher community to learn and apply PIDs in their documenting and reporting process. In the project, we engage with researchers, tools and platforms, and funding and research-producing organizations to piece together a complete picture of the FAIR research lifecycle.

FAIR Entities

For research outputs to be FAIR, it is important for entities associated with research activities to be clearly identified and kept accounted for. Assigning PIDs to these entities and citing these entities using their PIDs in the research communication and reporting process will help reduce administrative overhead and reliably track the credit for researchers and impact of research work.

Specifically, the most prominent entities that are currently supported are researchers (ORCID iD), research institutes and/or organizations (ROR ID), funding agencies (ROR ID, Crossref Funder Registry) and grants (registering DOIs for grants). Creating, requesting, or simply finding out the PIDs of these entities involved in a research project is the first step towards building a FAIR research workflow.

FAIR Practices

FAIR practices in the research process are varied, but the principle is simple: identify, share, and reuse/cite research outputs in a timely, consistent, and transparent manner.

Identifying points of improvement, understanding the relevant workflows, and formulating an adoption plan with the current practice in mind are some of the preparatory steps for adopting FAIR practices.

Main FAIR practices for researchers emphasized in this report are making a data management plan, selecting FAIR supporting tools and platforms for output sharing, and actively generating rich metadata as the research proceeds.

FAIR Supporting Structures

The FAIR supporting structures are the technological infrastructures that underpin scholarly communication, preservation, tracking and curation. These include the PID and metadata infrastructure, and the tools and platforms that integrate PIDs and metadata-sharing features on top of the services they provide.

Examples featured in this report include DOI, ORCID, and RAiD identifier systems, Dryad data repository, the OSF, the DMPTool, CEDAR metadata workbench, ChronosHub Open Access publishing service, and many others like preprint servers.

FAIR Outputs

The FAIR Output is an extension of FAIR research data, which is one type of output. Outputs are where the FAIRness - Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability manifest. To make outputs FAIR, the resources should be assigned with a persistent and globally unique identifier and annotated with rich metadata that describes, among other things, the output itself and its relation with other relevant outputs (full evaluation metrics see (Devaraju et al., 2020)).

Box 1. Key components of FAIR Workflows

Figure 1. A Diagram of the proposed FAIR Workflows based on a research lifecycle.

The FAIR Workflows cycle was conceptualized based on a general research lifecycle (Figure 1). Starting from the grant application stage (corresponding to stage 1 on Figure 1), researchers, institutes, and funders are encouraged to register and use their respective PIDs as a core component in the administrative processes.

When the grant application is approved, a new identifier should be created (by the funder, through registering the grant in a registry) for the project and enter the reporting cycle (stage 2). Researchers or institutes can also create a project portal with associated PID based on the grant approval to keep track of the project related information and outputs.

Data management planning (stage 3) is increasingly required by funding agencies as part of the application portfolio or project management package; prominent examples include the US National Science Foundation⁵ and the National Institutes of Health⁶, as well as the European Commission Horizon 2020 programme⁷. Developing a data management plan will help anchor the entire research process in terms of building the research around reproducibility principles and FAIR sharing. Registering a PID for the DMP can facilitate output tracking and discoverability.

Reproducible and FAIR research emphasizes the crucial importance of the research design process (stage 4). Registered reports, pre-registrations, and experimental protocols that outline proposed methods are all essential outputs generated at this stage of the research project. Sharing research methods pre-experiment helps the researcher to engage the community early in the process to build robust methods and to eliminate reporting bias.

During the experimenting process (stage 5), developing a documentation system that captures the key metadata of the research, experiments, and data captured is key to providing provenance and contextual information to the research outputs and making them reproducible and reusable. Adopting a community-endorsed, domain-specific metadata template into the documentation workflow helps to systemize FAIR practices.

Once the experiments are done, researchers can report related outputs (stage 6) such as data, protocols, analysis code, etc., and link these to the project, the pre-registration, the researchers, and their affiliation by citing the PIDs in the submission process.

Increasingly, researchers share their manuscripts publicly as preprints on discipline-focused preprint servers (stage 7) to communicate new findings and solicit community feedback while

⁵ <https://www.nsf.gov/bfa/dias/policy/dmp.jsp>

⁶ <https://sharing.nih.gov/data-management-and-sharing-policy>

⁷ https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/cross-cutting-issues/open-access-dissemination_en.htm

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going through the usually protracted peer-review process. When preprint servers assign a DOI for the document, it can be associated with the final publication in the metadata submitted to Crossref by the publisher (stage 8), thus concluding the FAIR cycle of research.

Integration workflow

To enable the seamless ingestion and exchange of metadata behind the scenes that make FAIR research possible, research tools and platforms are in the position to leverage the open scholarly infrastructure to easily integrate, and provide features that help various stakeholders identify, connect, and cite research inputs and outputs.

Integrators

Figure 2. Integration partners in the FAIR Workflows project,

The workflow provides a general framework for planning and evaluating existing support and gaps in infrastructure. In the project, we have a number of partner organizations providing a range of different research services and platforms; together they can support all the research activities throughout the research lifecycle.

Infrastructure/tool/platform	Role in the workflow
DataCite ⁸ , Crossref ⁹ , ORCID ¹⁰ , ROR ¹¹ , ARDC (RAiD) ¹²	Infrastructure for persistent identifiers that facilitate metadata distribution and system interoperability.
Dryad ¹³	General purpose open data repository with curation for data publications, acting as the designated data repository for the research project.
DMPTool ¹⁴	Machine actionable data management plan authoring platform, supporting the DMP workflows.
CEDAR ¹⁵	Metadata workbench that supports the authoring of metadata templates bolstered with standardized semantic resources.
ChronosHub ¹⁶	Open Access publishing management for funders, institutes, publishers, and researchers.
Open Science Framework (OSF) ¹⁷	Platform that supports collaborative research workflow by providing accessibility control and integrations with other tools.

Table 1. Infrastructure and integrators and their role in the FAIR workflows project

⁸ <https://datacite.org/>

⁹ <https://www.crossref.org/>

¹⁰ <https://orcid.org/>

¹¹ <https://ror.org/>

¹² <https://ardc.edu.au/services/ardc-identifier-services/raid-research-activity-identifier-service/>

¹³ <https://datadryad.org/>

¹⁴ <https://dmptool.org/>

¹⁵ <https://cedar.metadatascenter.org/>

¹⁶ <https://chronoshub.io/>

¹⁷ <https://osf.io/>

Existing integrations

Figure 3. Existing integrations among systems at the beginning of the project (gray lines).

Shown on the graph are some of the existing integrations among these systems.

1. OSF supports DataCite DOI registration for project page and pre-registrations.
2. DMPTool supports DMP ID (DataCite DOI) registration for data management plans authored using the platform.
3. Dryad supports DataCite DOI registration for datasets published through Dryad.
4. Protocols.io supports Crossref DOI registration for reproducible methods published on the platform.
5. Crossref, DataCite, ORCID, and ROR have interoperability built-in through connection metadata and service integrations such as Event Data and ORCID Claiming.

New integrations

Figure 4. New integrations among systems planned in the project (dark lines).

In the project we plan to establish new connections by implementing the following integrations (shown in the graph with dark blue links):

1. CEDAR - DataCite integration that allows researchers to publish and reuse domain specific metadata templates.
2. DMPTool - CEDAR integration that allows researchers to attach relevant CEDAR templates to planned outputs.
3. Dryad - CEDAR integration that allows researchers to deposit domain specific metadata alongside datasets, during the submission process on Dryad.

4. ChronosHub - Dryad integration that allows researchers to associate a related dataset to a manuscript, or prompt researchers to submit a related dataset to Dryad, during the manuscript submission process.
5. ChronosHub - DataCite integration that provides researchers with potentially related datasets to be associated with a manuscript during the manuscript submission process.
6. ARDC - DataCite integration to ensure interoperability between RAiD and DataCite DOIs by accommodating related identifiers and appropriate relation types in the metadata schema.

Specifically, with each of the project partners we've identified areas of work to address these use cases:

The Center for Expanded Data Annotation and Retrieval (CEDAR)

CEDAR provides the CEDAR Workbench, a metadata template authoring platform. Through better interfaces, terminology, metadata practices, and analytics, CEDAR helps scientific researchers and analysts create and use better metadata.

Enable DOI registration for CEDAR metadata artifacts

CEDAR will work with DataCite to integrate with the DataCite REST API to enable DOI registration for published metadata templates and instances (artifacts). CEDAR will implement the necessary processes to collect mandatory metadata information about CEDAR metadata artifacts, and a Subject property that uses the OECD Field of Science classification, which will act as an important point of reference for platforms that look to incorporate domain specific metadata information into their system. The DOI should resolve to a landing page for every metadata artifact.

CEDAR will work with DataCite to determine the appropriate resource type for metadata artifacts. It is instrumental for the template(s) built in the project to obtain DOIs so that they can be uniquely identified and cited in subsequent studies that produce comparable outputs, and enable discoverability of domain-specific data through the PIDGraph.

DMPTool

The DMPTool is a free, open-source, online application that helps researchers create data management plans (DMPs)¹⁸.

Support inclusion of CEDAR template information for outputs

¹⁸ <https://dmptool.org/about-us>

DMPTool is in the position to provide the opportunity for researchers to specify the metadata templates to be used in the research project when creating their data management plan, specifically during the “adding outputs” step.

DMPTool will implement a related metadata template field on the Research Output page with suggested templates pre-populated through the DataCite API, based on resource type and subject area. DMPTool will then include the DOI of the template in the metadata of the DMP as a related identifier.

Dryad

Dryad is an open source, community driven project that takes a unique approach to data publication and digital preservation.¹⁹ In the project, Dryad commits to address the use case of hosting extended domain specific metadata of data publication.

Integrate neuroscience metadata template(s) in the data deposition workflow

Dryad will integrate the CEDAR Embeddable Editor component to allow researchers to select and fill out appropriate metadata templates during the data deposition process. The discipline-specific metadata created will be saved and made publicly available alongside the datasets being deposited. When a template is selected by a researcher to accompany the data deposition, Dryad will include the DOI of the template in the DOI metadata of the dataset as a related identifier.

Dryad will work with DataCite to determine the relation type for associating metadata template and dataset through the relatedIdentifier property, and insert the relation type in the DOI metadata.

ChronosHub

Chronos Hub’s vision is to streamline the publishing processes across the research ecosystem, with the aim to minimize administration and accelerate research and innovation.

ChronosHub/Dryad integration to enable data deposition in the manuscript submission workflow

ChronosHub will integrate the Dryad submission workflow via the Dryad API, into the manuscript submission process on ChronosHub (Embedding Dryad's Submission into a Manuscript System), Dryad will provide necessary support for the integration (for detail, see Dryad’s contribution). When available, ChronosHub will collect the linkage information between dataset and paper, and submit it to related publishers and funders.

In this project, the researcher will be provided with the option to link a related dataset to their manuscript. The researcher can either be guided to include information about an existing dataset on Dryad when entering information about the manuscript, or in the case when the data has not

¹⁹ https://datadryad.org/stash/our_platform

been deposited, be redirected to Dryad to do so. ChronosHub will display the data submission status on the interface for manuscript submission, and share the subsequent manuscript status to Dryad when possible.

Enabling data and DMP suggestion in the manuscript submission process via integration with the DataCite API

ChronosHub will integrate the DataCite REST API to implement the ability to suggest datasets and DMPs within the manuscript submission workflow. Through the integration, ChronosHub will query DataCite metadata to identify datasets/DMPs that might be related to the manuscript being submitted. Authors using ChronosHub can then select relevant items and include related information when entering manuscript information during the submission process. ChronosHub will collect the linkage information between dataset, DMP, and article, and send it to the relevant publishers and funders to enable them to add this to their metadata.

The DataCite API allows users to query resources based on author (ORCID) and institute (ROR) (among others) information, which are some of the fields that ChronosHub will collect from the users as part of the profile building process. ChronosHub will then be able to suggest datasets and DMPs that are potentially related to the study based on the authors and their affiliations during the manuscript submission workflow.

Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC)

The strength of ARDC's Research Activity Identifier (RAiD) is its flexibility to link activities on different levels to capture research workflows in a more granular manner, e.g., a research project will include two complementary studies/experiments, and each experiment will be preceded by a series of pilot experiments.

In the project, ARDC will work with DataCite to explore the metadata properties to be included in the RAiD metadata schema to support RAiD use cases, and to implement a metadata exchange mechanism that support the interoperability of RAiD with the PIDGraph.

Identify relevant RAiD metadata fields for research projects/ activities based on the reality of the research workflow

ARDC will work with DataCite and the researchers at the Max Planck Institute of Empirical Aesthetics (MPIEA) to create a list of metadata properties for the RAiD schema that capture the essential information of research activities, building on the existing RAiD schema. The revised schema should support relationships between RAiD and other identifiers.

Identify relevant DataCite metadata fields to enable connections to RAiDs

ARDC will work with DataCite to create guidelines on referencing RAIDs from the DataCite metadata schema. This may include identifying an appropriate relatedIdentifierType and resourceTypeGeneral for RAiD entities, as well as appropriate relationTypes for linking RAiD to different types of resources.

Enhancing existing integrations

Figure 5. Previously existing integrations that are being enhanced in the project (sky blue lines).

We also plan to enhance two existing connections by adding more and better quality metadata to the metadata pipeline, by implementing the following:

1. Enhancement of DMPTool - DataCite integration: on top of the basic implementation of the DMP ID registration workflow, add further support for the addition of connection metadata for subsequent research outputs to the DMP metadata record.
2. Enhancement of Dryad - DataCite integration: on top of the basic implementation of DOI registration workflow at the point of dataset publication, further support the addition of

connection metadata of related domain specific metadata products (metadata template and instance) to the dataset metadata record.

DMPTool

Support addition of related works to DMPs by researchers

DMPTool will conduct user research necessary to determine the strategy for implementing a mechanism that allows researchers to add related works to the DMP, after the DMP has been made public and registered a DMP ID/ DOI.

DMPTool will then implement the functionality based on the recommendations. This will enable researchers to continuously make additions to the list of works related to the DMP during the project lifecycle, and update the DMP ID metadata with related identifiers.

The integration should ensure that the linkages between the DMP and related works will be expressed with appropriate resource type and relation type metadata. DataCite will work with DMPTool to determine the combinations.

This work needs to be done so that in cases where the downstream publishing platforms don't support references/relationship metadata very well, the researcher can step in and add those relationships through their own DMP - the metadata of which they control. An example is an experiment protocol published on protocols.io, which does not collect information about related resources in the metadata for DOI registration.

Dryad

Formalize the relation type metadata assignment of data/metadata template resource pair

Dryad will work with DataCite to determine the relation type for associating metadata template and dataset through the relatedIdentifier property, and insert the relation type in the DOI metadata.

Researcher Workflow

The researcher workflow consists of a series of smaller tasks that can be embedded in the daily activities of a researcher or a research team. These mainly consist of identifying sharable outputs (in the sense of recognizing something is sharable, and registering identifiers for them), selecting appropriate tools/platforms to support the production and publication, and making a habit of citing researcher, affiliation/organizations, funder/grant, and related outputs by their PIDs.

The arrangement of this section is based on the stages of the research lifecycle above and corresponding outputs for the purpose of simplicity. However, implementing FAIR workflows—like research itself—is a non-linear process and will call for constant evaluation from the researchers to introduce, test, and formalize sharing practices and their associated preparatory steps, while further, readjusting, or even avoiding some others, based on actual needs in terms of building reproducible and reusable research.

1. Grant application

Although practices differ by discipline, before the start of a research project, researchers usually will work through a grant application process to raise funds for the planned research work. Traditionally, processes and documents produced in the grant application and approval process are internally managed and there are few reliable ways to associate researchers to the grant they are awarded, or for the funder to track the research made possible by their grant.

In order to facilitate fair crediting and output tracking, at this stage, researchers, funders, and research institutes can each establish workflows around PID registration and application in the subsequent research activities.

- Key activity: Researchers to obtain an ORCID and use their ORCID iDs during the application process (and subsequent research process).

Entity	Researcher
Supporting structure	ORCID
PID	ORCID iD
Metadata	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Ensure the ORCID iD of a researcher is included in the metadata of all of the outputs they created or contributed to.

Researchers are encouraged to include their ORCID iDs in the documents required by the grant application process, and enter them, when possible, in grant application systems.

ORCID is increasingly integrated with research tools and platforms to make it easy for researchers to unambiguously associate themselves to their outputs. Using ORCID early and throughout the research process will help not only the researchers to take fair credits, but also streamline output tracking for funders and institutions.

- Key activity: Researchers to include the ROR ID of their affiliated institute/organization during the application process.

Entity	Institute
Supporting structure	ROR
PID	ROR ID
Metadata	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure ROR is included in metadata of subsequent outputs, e.g. through use of the affiliation identifier field.

ROR is in some cases integrated into reporting systems where affiliation information is required. Researchers don't usually need to know the ROR ID of their institution to use and benefit from them. However, when ROR is not integrated in the system being used, researchers are encouraged to suggest such an integration so that the affiliation information is more discoverable.

2. Grant registration

Funders play an important role in introducing, advocating, and enforcing the use of PIDs in the research and reporting process. One starting point is for funders to use a ROR ID for themselves, and provide instructions for usage.

- Key activity: Funder to obtain an organization PID to self-identify.

Entity	Funding agency
Supporting structure	ROR, Crossref
PID	ROR ID, Crossref Funder ID
Metadata	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide instructions to the awardees to include the ROR ID and Crossref Funder ID in the metadata of subsequent outputs, e.g. through the use of the award information field.

- Key activity: Funder to assign Grant ID once the grant is awarded, and to provide the Grant ID to the awardees and instruction for the application of Grant ID in reportable outputs.

Entity	Grant registration
Supporting structure	Crossref
PID	Grant ID
Metadata	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure the ORCID iDs of the awardees, and the ROR IDs of their affiliations are included in the metadata of the Grant ID. • Ensure the Grant ID is included in the metadata of subsequent outputs, e.g. through the use of an award information field.

Once the grant is awarded, it is advised for the funder to register a PID for the grant to aid the output tracking process. Crossref provides a service for grant registration which generates metadata records identified by DOIs that are able to be linked with outputs, activities, people, and organizations.²⁰

3. DMP submission

Data management plans have become one of the more formalized and acknowledged document types required by funders and institutes, either as a part of a project proposal, or as an integral part of the project management deliverables (Spichtinger, 2022). When not requested, researchers are still encouraged to plan for the various aspects of output management. While possible to start from scratch, most researchers rely on instructions and templates provided by the funder or institute to develop the DMP. Tools exist to aid the process.

DMPTool goes beyond presenting funder endorsed DMP templates as online forms; it supports the metadata and DOI registration of DMPs and the association with authors, funders, and related work within the metadata, making the DMP a machine-readable living document that continuously contributes to the FAIRness of the research with which it is associated.

- Key activities:
 - Researcher to develop and share DMP.
 - Researcher to associate outputs with the DMP.

Output	Data management plan
Supporting structure	DMPTool (collaborative authoring, sharing), General purpose data

²⁰ <https://www.crossref.org/community/grants/>

	repository (sharing)
PID	DMP ID (DataCite DOI)
Metadata connections	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure the ORCID iDs of the researchers, and the ROR IDs of the affiliations are included in the metadata of the DMP. • Include the DMP ID (DOI) of the DMP in any subsequent outputs that are related to the DMP and the project. • When DMP is machine actionable, ensure the inclusion of output PIDs in the metadata of the DMP through the related identifier property. • When appending outputs to DMP is not possible, ensure the DMP ID is included in the metadata of the subsequent outputs, through the related identifier field.

Researchers can use DMP authoring tools other than the DMPTool or manually create a DMP. In the case where no DMP ID is automatically assigned at the completion of the DMP, the final version of the DMP should be deposited to an open general purpose repository to be registered and obtain a DOI. The DMP metadata should include the PIDs for related researchers, organizations, and grant information.

- Key activity: Researcher or research administrator to consider registering project identifier.

Output	Project identifier
Supporting structure	ARDC
PID	RAiD
Metadata connections	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure the ORCIDs of the researchers, the ROR IDs of the affiliations and funding agencies, and the associated Grant ID(s) are included in the metadata of the project identifier. • Ensure the project identifier is cited in the metadata of subsequent outputs.

Registering an identifier for the research project is another way to organize activities and resources associated with it. ARDC's Research Activity Identifier (RAiD) is an emerging project identification scheme that aids this process.

- Key activity: Researcher to consider establishing a project page on OSF.

Output	Project page
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Supporting structure	OSF (collaborative working, sharing)
PID	DataCite DOI
Metadata connections	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure the researchers collaborating on the project register for an OSF account and associate the account with their ORCID iD, so that the ORCID iDs are embedded in the project metadata.

Researchers can also obtain project IDs through OSF by creating a project page on the platform. On the OSF platform, the Project page documents the core information about a project and acts as a central portal where different components of the projects are connected and displayed.

4. Research design

The research design process yields many important outputs that are the heart of reproducibility and reusability. Many organizations have started to support method-sharing practices, which are gradually gaining popularity in the research community.

- Key activity: Researcher to consider submitting a registered report.

Output	Registered Report (RR)
Supporting structure	Journals supporting the publication of registered reports ²¹ (publishing)
PID	Crossref DOI
Metadata connections	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure the ORCIDs of the researchers, the ROR IDs of the affiliations, and the Grant ID are included in the metadata of the RR. • When available, ensure the DOIs of the preceding outputs are included in the RR metadata, e.g. DMP ID, project ID. • Ensure the DOI of the RR is included in the metadata of the subsequent outputs from the proposed experiment described in the report.

A registered report is a type of formal publication that outlines the research questions and proposed methodology for peer review before the experiment or data collection is started²². An increasing number of journals are committed to accepting and publishing registered reports to

²¹ <https://www.cos.io/initiatives/registered-reports>

²² <https://www.cos.io/initiatives/registered-reports>

support best practice by eliminating publication biases²³. Aside from citing the DOI of the RR in the metadata of other outputs, it is important to associate the DOI of the RR with the final publication when available.

- Key activity: Researcher to consider developing and sharing pre-registrations.

Output	Pre-registration
Supporting structure	OSF (collaborative authoring, sharing), study registries
PID	DataCite DOI
Metadata connections	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure the researchers collaborating on the project register for an OSF account and associate the account to their ORCID iD, so that the ORCID iDs are embedded in the pre-registration metadata. • Use the OSF reporting function on the registration page to associate the PIDs of the related outputs to the pre-registration document.

A pre-registration is a time-stamped, immutable declaration of the research plan prior to beginning the study, put in place to separate the hypothesis-generating (exploratory) from hypothesis-testing (confirmatory). Sharing pre-registration and experiment results separately helps increase the rigor of research and decreases problematic research practices.

- Key activity: Researcher to create rich metadata for research activities by keeping metadata records.

Output	Metadata template
Supporting structure	CEDAR
PID	DataCite DOI
Metadata connections	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure the researchers collaborating on the metadata template register for a CEDAR account and associate the account to their ORCID iD, so that the ORCID iDs are embedded in the template metadata. • Ensure the template DOI is included in the metadata of subsequent data and paper publications.

²³ <https://royalsociety.org/blog/2016/11/registered-reports-what-are-they-and-why-are-they-important/>

Metadata is essential for the FAIRness of research. CEDAR provides a solution to enable the use of standardized domain-specific semantic resources in metadata records. Making CEDAR templates citable will help promote the practice.

Domain-specific metadata templates increase their usefulness as their adoption grows. Obtaining community endorsement and recommendation for the set of core metadata elements in the template is one of the most important ways to gain usage. Researchers are encouraged to seek existing efforts around metadata standardization in the disciplinary community, to evaluate, adopt, and contribute to on-going projects. If necessary, start new open initiatives with collaborative procedures. The GO FAIR Metadata for Machines Workshops²⁴ provide a good model for such initiatives.

5. Experiment conducted

- Key activity: Researcher to build experimental protocol and keep thorough notes when conducting experiments using new protocols or reusing existing protocols.

Output	Experiment protocols
Supporting structure	Protocols.io (collaborative authoring, sharing), Labarchives ²⁵
PID	Crossref DOI, DataCite DOI
Metadata connections	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Ensure the researchers collaborating on the protocol register for a protocols.io account and associate the account to their ORCID iD, so that the ORCID iDs are embedded in the protocol publication.• Ensure the DOI of the published protocol is included in the subsequent outputs, such as data collected using the protocol, conference and formal publication that reports about the experiment that was conducted based on the protocol, etc.

Like pre-registrations and registered reports, experimental protocols provide crucial contextual information that increases the reproducibility of research. The protocol and experiment notes are produced in this stage but are sometimes considered only sharable after the experiment and analysis are done (in the next stage). Which output PIDs are available for citing/including with the protocols depends on when the protocol is shared.

- Key activity: Researcher to publicly communicate the progress and interim outputs.

²⁴ <https://www.go-fair.org/resources/go-fair-workshop-series/metadata-for-machines-workshops/>

²⁵ <https://www.labarchives.com/>

Output	Conference paper, poster, presentation
Supporting structure	General purpose repository (sharing)
PID	DataCite DOI, Crossref DOI
Metadata connections	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure the ORCIDs of the researchers, and the ROR IDs of the affiliations are included in the metadata of the output. • Ensure the Funder ID/ROR ID and the Grant ID are included in the metadata of the output.

General purpose repositories that are integrated with DOI registration functions are important infrastructure for the sharing and citing of interim scholarly outputs. When publicly shared, conference posters and presentations provide anchor points for research efforts that increase transparency and accountability.

6. Research code, data, and other outputs deposited

The data analysis stage of the research is also output rich, starting from the data collected in the previous stage.

- Key activity: Researcher to prepare and share dataset.

Output	Dataset
Supporting structure	Dryad (sharing/ publishing), other repository (sharing/ publishing)
PID	DataCite DOI
Metadata connections	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure the ORCIDs of the researchers, and the ROR IDs of the affiliations are included in the metadata of the output. • When possible, specify the contributor role of the researchers in the project. • Ensure the Funder ID/ROR ID and the Grant ID are included in the metadata of the dataset. • Cite the DOI of the dataset in the manuscript.

Data sharing is arguably one of the most important FAIR practices, as the FAIR principles are designed for research data. Exposing research data underpinning the published research is increasingly being advised by funders, institutes, and publishers, in the effort to make data research outputs as important as formal publications.

- Key activity: Researcher to prepare and share data analysis scripts.

Output	Code/software, analysis workflows
Supporting structure	Zenodo (sharing/ publishing in collaboration with github), Brainlife (collaborative data analysis, workflow sharing), other repository (sharing/ publishing)
PID	DataCite DOI
Metadata connections	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure the ORCIDs of the researchers, and the ROR IDs of the affiliations are included in the metadata of the code. • Ensure the Funder ID/ROR ID and the Grant ID are included in the metadata of the code. • Ensure the DOI of the data the code was originally applied to is included in the metadata of the code.

The Zenodo/Github integration provides researchers with a streamlined workflow to package code on Github to be shared on Zenodo where a DOI and associated metadata are registered.

Brainlife²⁶ provide a platform for customized neuroscience analysis workflow building and publishing, it supports DOI registration for bundled workflow and outputs, making them independently citable.

- Key activity: Researcher to share other types of interim outputs.

Output	Pilot report, notebook, ELN document
Supporting structure	Dryad (sharing/ publishing), Labarchives (ELN coauthoring, sharing), other repository (sharing/ publishing)
PID	DataCite DOI
Metadata connections	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure the ORCIDs of the researchers, and the ROR IDs of the affiliations are included in the metadata of the output. • When possible, specify the contributor role of the researchers in the project. • Ensure the Funder ID/ROR ID and the Grant ID are included in the metadata of the dataset. • Cite the DOI of the dataset in the manuscript.

When using Dryad, it is advised to package the data, analysis code, and software related to a paper in a single dataset publication. Researchers can also deposit any of these elements separately on other general-purpose repositories if deemed reusable independently.

²⁶ <https://brainlife.io/about/>

7. Preprint submitted

- Key activity: Researcher to submit the manuscript to a preprint server.

Output	Preprint
Supporting structure	(Psy)ArXiv (sharing), other preprint servers
PID	DataCite or Crossref DOI
Metadata connections	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure the ORCIDs of the researchers, and the ROR IDs of the affiliations are included in the metadata of the preprint. • Ensure the Funder ID/ROR ID and the Grant ID are included in the metadata of the preprint. • When possible, include the DOI of the data in the metadata of the preprint. • Ensure the DOI of the preprint is cited in the manuscript submitted to journals.

Sharing manuscripts on preprint servers before officially submitting to journals is increasingly being adopted by the researcher community. Registering DOIs facilitates the sharing, reviewing, and citation of preprints and accelerates the communication of research results.

8. Research article published

Including all the PIDs used in the workflow described here in the metadata of the journal article is an effective way to increase the discoverability of the numerous outputs generated and produced during the research lifecycle.

- Key activity: Researcher to submit the manuscript to a journal.

Output	Paper
Supporting structure	ChronosHub (OA publishing management), Journal publishing system (publishing), Crossref
PID	Crossref DOI
Metadata connections	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure the ORCIDs of the researchers, and the ROR IDs of the affiliations are included in the metadata of the paper. • Ensure the Funder ID/ROR ID and the Grant ID are included in the metadata of the paper. • Ensure related data is cited in the paper and the DOI of the dataset is included in the article metadata.

Registering content with Crossref to be identified with Crossref DOIs is a standard practice for a vast amount of academic publishers; however, there is still room for the quality of the metadata submissions to improve. Including connection information in the metadata of the paper not only fulfills FAIR compliance requirements, but also helps promote the practice of output sharing by increasing discoverability.

Conclusion

Being mindful of the underlying metadata, and effectively applying available PIDs by adopting PID integrated tools and platforms is essential for making research FAIR. There are numerous decisions and judgment calls researchers will need to make while practicing FAIR, even after gaining an in-depth understanding of the Open and FAIR research landscape. We encourage researchers to carefully evaluate and design their own workflows that integrate FAIR practices efficiently and organically, while considering not only the reproducibility and reusability of outputs, but also the disciplinary/ institution/ team conventions. With this workflow specification document, we hope to contribute to efforts toward making FAIR workflows actionable, implementable, and achievable.